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A New Spectrophotometric Determination of O, O-Diethyl o-p nitrophenyl thiophosphate (Parathion) Residues in Plant Materials and Soil

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PARATHION is one of the most widely used nonsystemic contact insecticide¹. Various instrumental methods²⁻⁴ are available in the literature for its determination. The present communication proposes a new method based on the reduction of nitro group of parathion to amino group⁵, which is subsequently diazotised and coupled with α -naphthol to form an azo dye in alkaline medium. The dye shows an absorbance maxima at 500 nm. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of parathion in various plant materials and soil.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss spekol with 1 cm matched cell was used.

Reagent : A 1 mg ml⁻¹ of parathion in 50% ethanol and a 10 μ g ml⁻¹ solution as working standard were used. Zinc dust (A.R.) 5 M HCl, 0.25% aqueous solution of NaNO₂, 3% aqueous solution of sulphamic acid, 0.1 M aqueous solution of EDTA ; 0.2% aqueous solution of α -naphthol and 5 M NaOH solution were used.

Procedure : To an aliquot containing 10–83 μ g of parathion were added zinc dust (1 g) and 5 M HCl (2 ml). The contents were boiled for 2 min, followed by gentle heating for 10 min. The mixture was then cooled and filtered and to it sodium nitrite solution (1 ml) was added and kept for 10 min with occasional shaking. During diazotisation the acidity was adjusted to 0.5–2 M HCl. α -Naphthol solution (2 ml) was then added followed by sulphamic acid (1 ml) and EDTA (1 ml) solutions. The solution was kept for 3 min and made alkaline with an excess of sodium hydroxide to produce an azo dye. The absorbance of the dye was measured at 500 nm against reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

A time 10 min each for reduction and diazotisation and 5 min for coupling were required. A temperature 15–30° was most suitable for complete diazotisation and coupling. Full colour development occurred at or above pH 11. Reagent concentration of 1 g of zinc and 2 ml of 5 M HCl

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF PARATHION IN VARIOUS PLANT MATERIALS AND SOIL*

Sample*	Parathion originally found (μ g)		Parathion added (μ g)	Total parathion found (μ g) **by		Difference (μ g) in		Recovery %	
	(A)	(B)		(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)	(A)	(B)
Tomato	23	20	20	43.5	39.0	20.5	19.0	102.5	95.0
	30	30	30	60.5	57.0	30.5	27.0	101.6	90.0
	21	20	20	40.5	37.5	19.5	17.5	97.5	87.5
Cauliflower	57	53	50	107.0	101.0	50.0	48.0	100.0	96.0
	55	52	50	101.0	99.0	46.0	44.0	92.0	88.0
	51	50	50	100.0	98.0	45.0	43.0	90.0	86.0
Cabbage	43	42	40	83.5	80.5	40.5	38.5	101.2	95.5
	45	43	40	85.0	77.4	40.0	34.4	100.0	86.0
	41	40	40	79.5	74.0	38.5	34.0	95.5	85.0
Runner beans	10	8	10	19.1	16.7	9.10	8.7	91.0	87.0
	12	11	10	21.9	19.5	9.90	8.5	99.0	85.0
	—	—	10	9.25	8.55	9.25	8.55	92.5	85.5
Spinach (different varieties)	—	—	10	9.10	8.75	9.10	8.75	91.0	87.5
	5	3	10	14.65	12.00	9.65	9.00	96.5	90.0
	7	4	10	16.58	12.40	9.58	8.4	95.8	84.0
Soil	44	40	40	81.48	75.2	37.48	35.2	93.7	88.0
	—	—	40	37.6	35.0	37.60	35.0	94.0	87.5
	18	15	20	36.9	32.3	18.90	17.3	94.5	86.5

* (A) = Proposed method, (B) = Buckley method (Ref. 4); Three sets of experiments done for each sample; Amount of sample = 25 g. ** Mean of three replicate analyses.

was required for complete reduction. 1 ml of sodium nitrite for diazotisation and 2 ml of α -naphthol solutions were sufficient for coupling.

Beer's law was obeyed in the range 0.4–3.3 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $6.98 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0042 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively for parathion. The reproducibility of the method was checked by analysing 25 $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$ of parathion for a period of 8 days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.0045 and $\pm 1.87\%$ respectively.

The following foreign species (in ppm) do not interfere in the estimation of 1 ppm parathion: Ca^{++} , Pb^{++} and Sr^{++} (upto 500), Cd^{++} , Mn^{++} and phosphate (upto 500), formaldehyde, Mg^{++} , Ni^{++} and Fe^{++} (upto 250), sulphate, aniline, phenol and Cu^{++} (upto 150), DDT, aldrin, endrin and malathion (upto 500).

Application: The method was applied in the determination of parathion in samples of vegetables foliage and soil.

The parathion was extracted from various crushed samples of vegetables and foiliages in n-hexane as reported⁴, and analysed by the proposed and compared with the Buckley⁴ method (Table 1).

Known amounts of finely ground soil samples were washed with ethanol ($2 \times 20 \text{ ml}$) and made upto the volume with demineralised water. An aliquot of this solution was then analysed by the proposed as well as by the Buckley⁴ method (Table 1).

The recoveries from the samples are better even without the removal of coloured pigments and in low levels, in comparison to other methods. Parathion and methyl parathion can be precisely determined down to 0.4 ppm using the proposed method.

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A New Spectrophotometric Method for Determination of Acrylonitrile in Traces and its Application to Biological Samples

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ACRYLONITRILE¹ is used in various industries and organic synthesis and is toxic. Various methods have been reported for its determination^{2,3}.

A new spectrophotometric method is reported here for the trace determination of acrylonitrile. Acrylonitrile is converted into cyanide on reacting with alkaline potassium permanganate⁴ and the cyanide so formed on reaction with saturated bromine water is converted into cyanogen bromide which reacts with pyridine to form glutaconic aldehyde and then coupled with aqueous phloroglucinol to give red-violet polymethine dye in alkaline medium which obeys Beer's law in the range of 10–70 μg per 10 ml of the final solution (1–7 ppm). The method has been successfully applied for the determination of acrylonitrile in air, blood and urine.

Experimental

A Carl Zeiss spekol and calibrated glassware were used. Analytical grade reagents and distilled water were used.

A solution (1 mg ml^{-1}) of acrylonitrile in 5% ethanol was prepared and a working standard of 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ solution was used. Alkaline potassium permanganate solution was prepared by mixing 0.1 N KMnO_4 (35 ml) with 0.1 N NaOH (15 ml). A 1.5% (w/v) aqueous solution of sodium arsenite and 2 M HCl were used.

Pyridine reagent was prepared by mixing freshly distilled pyridine (18 ml) with concentrated HCl (3 ml) and diluted with distilled water (12 ml). A saturated aqueous solution of phloroglucinol and bromine was used.

Procedure: To an aliquot containing 10 to 70 μg (1–7 ppm) of acrylonitrile, alkaline potassium permanganate solution (1 ml) was added and kept for 2 min. The excess of potassium permanganate was then decolourised by a few drops of sodium arsenite followed by 2 M HCl (0.2 ml). Then bromine solution (0.5 ml) was added and the excess bromine destroyed by the dropwise addition of sodium arsenite. To it pyridine reagent (0.3 ml) followed by phloroglucinol (1 ml) were added. After 1 min the volume was made upto the mark with sodium hydroxide to make pH of the final solution ~ 9 and then measured the absorbance